

**ПУТИ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ ФИНАНСОВОЙ УСТОЙЧИВОСТИ ЗА СЧЕТ
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ СИСТЕМЫ ОПЕРАТИВНОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ЭЛЕМЕНТАМИ
ОБОРОТНЫХ АКТИВОВ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ**

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**WAYS TO ENSURE FINANCIAL STABILITY THROUGH IMPROVEMENT OF THE SYSTEM OF
OPERATIONAL MANAGEMENT OF THE ELEMENTS OF CURRENT ASSETS OF ENTERPRISES**

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Аннотация

В статье рассматривается вопрос об обеспечении финансовой устойчивости за счет совершенствования системы оперативного управления элементами оборотных активов. Эффективное управление оборотными активами отвечает за нормальную работу предприятий, повышение уровня рентабельности производства и множество других факторов. В современных условиях, когда экономика под влиянием отрицательных ситуаций, негативная тенденция отражается и на изменении эффективности управления оборотными средствами. Повышение финансовой устойчивости и платежеспособности компании напрямую зависит рациональное и эффективное использование оборотных активов.

Abstract

The article deals with the issue of ensuring financial stability by improving the system of operational management of elements of current assets. Effective management of current assets is responsible for the normal operation of enterprises, increasing the level of profitability of production and many other factors. In modern conditions, when the economy is under the influence of negative situations, the negative trend is also reflected in the change in the efficiency of working capital management. Increasing the financial stability and solvency of the company directly depends on the rational and efficient use of current assets.

Ключевые слова: финансовая устойчивость, эффективное управление, оборотные средства, хозяйственный механизм, система управления.

Keywords: financial stability, effective management, current asset, economic mechanism, management system.

In world practice, it is considered expedient to acquire working capital through short-term loans, since working capital should bring more income than the loan fee.

Introduction.

Increasing the business activity of industrial enterprises requires continuous improvement of the operational management system of current assets under the influence of internal and external environmental factors. Although effective management of current assets embodies the process of investing existing working capital into current assets, it creates the necessary conditions for the successful operation of not only an industrial enterprise, but also the entire economy on a macro scale. In a highly competitive economic environment, every business entity strives to maximize the use of available funds, and an increase in the rate of turnover of current assets reduces the need for them. As a result, the optimal management of current assets focused on the above-mentioned final results creates conditions for each business entity to attract debt funds and in this process to minimize the need to attract funds from financial markets to improve solvency.

Theoretical and methodological aspects of research

Its improvement is carried out by the introduction of modern types of functional elements of this management, optimization of the economic mechanism embodying the interconnection and logical connection between them. Russian economist V.A. According to Ryazanova, the instruments of such an economic mechanism are planning, control system, regulatory instruments, revenue and cost levers as levers[1]. Types of current assets can be considered as elements, namely: production reserves, receivables, financial investments and cash[2]. The mechanism that ensures the interaction of the above components of the operational management system of current assets can work effectively through a communication system that has the characteristic of information exchange[3].

In the present conditions, the traditional mechanism of operational management of current assets in local industrial enterprises is mainly organized on the basis of efficiency indicators such as effective use of production resources, minimization of costs, increase of labor productivity by increasing turnover and profitability of current assets. In our opinion, the traditional model of current asset management has a number of weaknesses in terms of strengthening the national and

international competitiveness of industrial enterprises. In particular, decisions aimed at managing individual elements of current assets are focused on the following responsibility centers for certain types of activities: production management, material and technical support management, sales processes and financial manage-

ment, etc[4]. Of course, the management of current assets is based on the decision-making paradigm of these responsibility centers [1][5]. But at the same time, these processes are not organized in a coherent relationship with the complex management system based on the effect of interaction and the strategic goals of enterprises.

Figure №1. Optimization of the operational management system of current assets¹

¹ The image is systematized by the author.

Figure №1 systematizes 2 main directions of optimization of the operative management system of current assets. These directions are systematized based on the analysis in our previous chapter based on a wide arsenal of factors affecting the effectiveness of the current asset management system in the asset management system of local industrial corporations. The first direction combines the directions of intensification of production activities, technological modernization and implementation of an effective sales policy[6]. As a result of the analysis, it was observed that in most industrial zones, the problems related to the sales policy at a moderate level of production capacity affect the low rate of income from the sale of goods. As a result, a high indicator of the accumulation level of the stock of finished products in the structure of current assets serves as a factor that negatively affects the indicator of the speed of current assets turnover. In this context, the first and third directions of technological optimization of operational activity will be ensured by the policy of effective sale of finished products, and as a result, a stable increase in income can be observed[2]. Of course, these measures incorporate the economic and financial instruments of operational management, and the increase in the index of business activity through the growth of

income will ultimately affect the increase in the turnover rate of the elements of current assets[7]. In this context, the first and third directions of technological optimization of operational activity will be ensured by the policy of effective sale of finished products, and as a result, a stable increase in income can be observed[8]. Of course, these measures incorporate the economic and financial instruments of operational management, and the increase in the index of business activity through the growth of income will ultimately affect the increase in the turnover rate of the elements of current assets.

Analysis and result of research

Generalized indicators of the effectiveness of current asset management are systematized in our research into 3 main categories: a) indicators of business activity. These indicators are mainly determined by their turnover in the cross-section of the elements of assets, and represent the interdependence of assets and financial results; b) assets are financial return or profitability indicators; c) indicators related to ensuring financial stability of assets[9]. Based on the practical data of the analyzed enterprises, the same scenario can be witnessed in the indicators of business activity according to some conclusions obtained in the above chapters.

Table №1

Analysis of indicators of business activity (assets and payables turnover) in enterprises²

Indicators/years	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
“Jizzakhplastmassa” JSC					
$K(t)a = R/(Am)$	1.26	1.52	1.00	0.54	0.41
$K(t)fa = R/(FAM)$	3.02	4.25	2.21	1.09	0.83
$K(t)ca = R/(CAM)$	1.65	2.37	1.84	1.09	0.80
$K(t)i = R/(Im)$	3.76	3.64	3.33	1.58	1.74
$K(t)ar = R/(ARm)$	5.16	6.42	14.63	2.14	1.83
$K(e)ap = R/(APm)$	4.63	9.75	9.09	4.28	3.02
“Kokon Mechanical Plant” JSC					
$K(t)a = R/(Am)$	0.87	1.00	0.82	0.34	0.14
$K(t)fa = R/(FAM)$	3.42	5.24	5.89	2.54	1.02
$K(t)ca = R/(CAM)$	1.44	1.24	0.96	0.40	0.17
$K(t)i = R/(Im)$	5.13	6.76	4.17	1.57	0.52
$K(t)ar = R/(ARm)$	1.51	2.15	2.52	1.22	0.68
$K(e)ap = R/(APm)$	3.34	2.10	1.50	0.57	0.22

As can be seen from the data in Table №1. Asset turnover ratio in JSC “Jizzakhplastmassa” in 2020-2021 ($K(t)a$) is below 0. In addition to turnover ($K(t)fa$) and turnover ratio of current assets ($K(t)ca$) indicators in 2021 were pact from 0. The turnover ratio of creditor debts fluctuated in the range of max 9.75 to min 3.02 during the analyzed period. This situation has affected the operational and financial cycle.

Asset turnover ratio at “Kokon Mechanical Plant” JSC ($K(t)a$) in 2019-2021, the rate was below 0. The turnover of current assets was also lower than 0 during

this period. The existence of the need for the industrial production process to be equipped with a high level of capital requires that the turnover of assets is relatively low compared to other industries. But if we take into account the fact that the turnover of current assets has a special description and is one of the main indicators of the efficiency of current assets, we can see that both companies are missing opportunities in terms of efficiency in this field. As a result, the period of circulation of current assets is even more than 1 calendar year in special cases.

² Joint-stock companies are calculated on the basis of annual balance sheet data.

Table №2

Analysis of indicators of business activity (assets and payables turnover period) in enterprises, in days³

Indicators/years	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
“Jizzakhplastmassa” JSC					
365/K(τ)a	290	240	365	676	890
365/K(t)fa	121	86	165	335	440
365/K(t) ca	221	154	198	335	456
365/K(t)i	97	100	110	231	210
365/K(t)ar	71	57	25	171	199
365/K(e)ap	79	37	40	85	121
“Kokon Mechanical Plant” JSC					
365/K(τ)a	420	365	445	1074	2607
365/K(t)fa	107	70	62	144	358
365/K(t) ca	253	294	380	913	2147
365/K(t)i	71	54	88	232	702
365/K(t)ar	242	170	145	299	537
365/K(e)ap	109	174	243	640	1659

In particular, according to Table №2 in 2021, the turnover period of current assets in “Jizzakhplastmassa” JSC is more than 1 calendar year, or more precisely, 456 days. This indicator is 2147 days in 2021 at “Ko’kan Mechanics Plant” JSC. Indicators of business activity in enterprises are mainly calculated using elements such as income from product sales, assets and payables, and we can see which of these elements affected the turnover indicator from the table below.

In “Jizzakhplastmassa” JSC, the income from

product sales in 2020-21 has not increased, but decreased (77% in 2020 and -84% in 2021). On the contrary, the stable growth of total assets due to the annual growth of non-current assets (by 156% in 2020 and 110% in 2021) and current assets (in 2020 - 131% and 114% in 2021) was a factor negatively affecting the turnover of assets. Especially JSC “Jizzakhplastmassa” in 2020 compared to 2019 we can see that the extremely high annual growth rate of receivables (529%) served as a factor negatively affecting the turnover of working capital.

Table №3

Average annual growth rate of income from product sales, assets and payables in enterprises⁴, in %

Indicators/years	2018	2019	2020	2021
“Jizzakhplastmassa” JSC				
Revenue from product sales	166	106	77	84
Total assets	138	161	142	112
Non-current assets	118	205	156	110
Current assets	116	137	131	114
TMZ	172	116	163	76
Accounts receivable	134	047	529	98
Accounts payable	79	114	164	119
“Kokan Mechanical Plant” JSC				
Revenue from product sales	143	96	39	40
Total assets	124	116	94	96
Non-current assets	93	85	91	100
Current assets	166	124	95	96
TMZ	109	155	104	122
Accounts receivable	100	82	81	72
Accounts payable	228	134	103	103

In JSC “Koqon Mechanics Plant” there was an annual increase in the value of goods material reserves along with an annual decrease in all elements of assets. Based on the above, the following conclusions can be systematized:

Firstly, an active investment policy was carried out in “Jizzakhplastmassa” JSC on modernization of production, new technological equipment of the main funds. Although this situation ensures a low level of

business activity (asset turnover) in the enterprise in the near term, in the medium term it can ensure a stable increase in the volume of production and profitability indicators due to the full operation of production facilities.

Secondly, in both enterprises, operational management practice aimed at ensuring the optimal size and proportions of production and circulation funds in the structure of current assets based on real production

³ Calculated by the author based on analyses.

⁴ Calculated by the author based on analyses.

needs did not have a systematic description.

Thirdly, the high level of receivables in the structure of current funds served as a factor that negatively affects the indicators of business activity. This situation requires the mobilization of internal reserves in asset management for the mass production process, the development of a mechanism for effective management of receivables and payables based on balanced indicators of financial stability.

In the international experience, there are modern methods of working in an organic relationship with suppliers and buyers, and through these methods, opportunities are created to form production reserves based not only on the needs of the optimal volume of production[10]. Perhaps, results will be achieved in terms of increasing the effectiveness of the policy of selling manufactured goods, effective management of receivables and payables in the context of ensuring balanced indicators of financial stability.

One such method is in the asset management system AVS-XYZ-analysis system is an optimization method. Management of receivables and payables based on the AVS-XYZ-analysis system is mainly aimed at balancing liquidity and solvency, and the approach of economists to categorization of debts is different.

In particular, the Russian economist N. A. Kalma-kova[11] In the analysis, AVS divided receivables into

categories based on the share of sales volume and the frequency of debt repayment, and payables were divided into categories based on the size and composition of available resources. In the XYZ-analysis system, receivables and payables are divided into categories according to the repayment terms. In general, the AVS-XYZ-analytical system based on this approach is implemented in the position of optimizing the process of formation of receivables based on the criteria of solvency. Also, as we have seen in our previous chapter, this methodology is considered important in making decisions on the optimization of working capital through the methods of the current asset management system.

In our approach, based on the AVS-XYZ-analysis system, we propose to divide receivables into 3 main categories: a) consumers (consumers of goods and services), customers (Dha; Dxb; Dxc) and suppliers, contractors (raw materials and semi-finished products) (Kha ; Kxb; Kxc) the degree of synchronization of the volume and frequency of receivables and payables; b) paid lump sum payments (Dya; Dyb; Dyc) and lump sum payments received (Kya; Kyb; Kyc) the degree of synchronization of the volume and frequency of receivables and payables; c) other receivables (Dza; Dzb; Dzc) and accounts payable (Dza; Dzb; Dzc) we will consider the analysis of the degree of synchronization of volume and frequency.

Table №4
 “Jizzakhplastmassa” JSCmatrix model of receivables optimization in asset management system⁵, mln. in sum

Classification / Value	Accounts receivable										Total	Balance (Deficit (-); Surplus (+))
	Mr	etc	Dxc	Dia	Dyb	Dyc	Dza	Dzb	Dzc	Total		
Xha	939.4	3887.7	7775.4	1295.9	130.7	108.9	196.1	84.4	168.8	28.1	13675.9	+2948.3
Kxb	1878.7		1878.7									+5896.7
Kxc	313.1			313.1								+982.8
Kya	414.9	2948.3	5896.7	982.8	130.7			-284.2				-284.2
Kyb	829.8					829.8		-720.9				-720.9
Kyc	138.3						138.3					+57.8
Kza	929.4						57.8	84.4			-844.9	-844.9
Kzb	1858.7								168.8		-1689.9	-1689.9
Kzc	309.8									28.1	-281.7	-281.7
Total	7612											+6063.9

The negative values in the parallel of the colored quadrants of the matrix mean the existence of a deficit in working capital for a certain period (mainly 1, 3 and 6 months) for the specified categories of receivables and payables. The positive values below the vertical column of the colored quadrants represent the value equivalents of the surplus in the specified categories of receivables and payables or the possibility of full closing of the respective payables. In this case, the surplus represents the ability to cover the corresponding creditor debts at the expense of the receivables of the specified category.

In 2021 balance sheet of “Jizzakhplastmassa” JSC was formed on the basis of statistical data on receiva-

bles and payables in current assets and current liabilities, and the current balance of receivables and payables +6063.9 mln. sum is creating a surplus. Consumers (consumers of goods and services), customers (Dha; Dxb; Dxc) and suppliers, contractors (raw materials and semi-finished products), the state of receivables and payables is creating a surplus, and due to its value, 3 and 6-month receivables and payables can be divided into coordination opportunities. From the analysis data, we can see that the value of the balance of receivables and payables on the right side of the matrix vertically in the first 3 columns above (+2948.3; +5896.7; +982.8) is having opportunities to compensate the value equivalent of the deficit in the following lines. Because the high share and surplus of receivables and

⁵Calculated by the author based on analyses.

payables for 1 month creates opportunities for the mobilization of internal reserves for financial operational needs aimed at ensuring the continuity of operational activities through the rapid transformation of current funds into cash.

So, "Jizzakhplastmassa" JSC the proposed matrix model of receivables optimization in the asset management system brings the following advantages to the working capital and, in particular, the current asset management system[12]:

1. At the expense of receivables, which are the main element of circulating funds in current assets: continuity of operational activity; internal financial and budget discipline; realistic possibilities of ensuring operational liquidity ability are assessed in the context of other receivables and payables.

2. Provides information on the level of internal synchronization of receivables and payables.

3. Based on the imbalance in the internal structure of receivables and payables based on retrospective data, it creates opportunities to introduce budgeting practices directed to each of their elements in the future.

When making a final decision, it is recommended to use the minimum value criterion in the approach based on the AVS-XYZ-analysis system[13]. Management decisions on the situation of excess receivables as

a source of paying creditors: it will be possible to systematically organize measures to invest temporarily consolidated financial resources in current assets, taking into account factors such as maturity, value equivalent volume, profitability and the risk of non-return of investments. One of the important mechanisms for effective management of receivables is to classify them according to criteria such as (a) their importance for the realization of the company's sales policy (volume of receivables), (b) orders and (c) the frequency of overdue receivables, and (d) the maturity of receivables. to identify organizations and to develop a differentiated policy mechanism for granting discounts for them.

Companies can use the cumulative method to classify important partners for the implementation of sales policy[14]. According to this method, the first 33 percent is assessed in the form of commercial credit to the group of buyers who purchase goods at the highest value. In this case, their high scores are mainly determined by the high percentage of the value of the purchased goods. Another important indicator is the frequency of repayment of receivables, and this indicator is of high importance in terms of strengthening the liquidity position of enterprises.

Table №5

Information for an integrated assessment of the receivables of partners⁶

Steps	Classification category	weight, β_n	Criteria	Evaluation points, X_n
Classification and assessment of debtors by sales volume				
1	A	0.4	Maximum volume	3
			Average size	2
			Minimum size	1
Classification and assessment of debtors according to the frequency of orders				
2	B	0.2	Quick orders	3
			Medium term orders	2
			Disposable cuffs	1
Classification and evaluation of debtors according to the terms of repayment of receivables				
3	S	0.2	Debts for 1 month	3
			Debts for 3 months	2
			Debts over 3 months	1
Categorizing and rating debtors by frequency of delinquent receivables				
4	D	0.2	In the last 3 years, there were no overdue receivables	3
			No overdue receivables were observed in the last 1 year	2
			Deferred arrears are observed for accounts payable	1

Based on the data in the above table, it is possible to evaluate the debtors in a point system based on 4 main factors. Based on each category (selected criteria) their weight in the total score (β) it is possible to calculate the integral rating score of each debtor among the total debtors. This assessment is carried out as follows:

$$A(X_n) \cdot 0.4 + B(X_n) \cdot 0.2 + C(X_n) \cdot 0.2 + D(X_n) \cdot 0.2 = \sum_{n=1}^n Y_n \cdot \beta_n$$

Based on the integral rating score based on the above formula, a register of receivables is created for the debtors, and the credit policy consisting of 4 blocks is allocated for the category of debtors in this register. According to the matrix in Table №6, debtors with the highest rating and the largest amount of receivables come under the credit policy regime in quadrant X11, and conditions are created for them to further expand the sale of goods on credit (X11).

⁶ Calculated by the author based on analyses.

A matrix of differentiated credit policies in relation to debtors⁷

Credit policy block \ Debtors	Top rated debtors	Debtors with good ratings	Medium rating debtors	Low rating debtors
Amount of receivables	X11	X12	X13	X14
Frequency of orders	X21	X22	X23	X24
Term of receivables	X31	X32	X33	X34
Frequency of delinquent accounts receivable	X41	X42	X43	X44

In the credit policy for debtors with a good rating and a high amount of receivables, conditions will be created for further expansion of credit sales with the conditions of further raising the rating indicator (X12). In the credit policy [15][16] for debtors with a medium rating and a high volume of receivables, the limits on the volume of credit sales are currently set (X13). For debtors with a low rating, but with a low rating reputation, the sale of goods on credit is limited in arithmetical progression during the months of the year (X14).

And in accordance with the degradation of debtors according to the frequency of orders: giving discounts for each additional order (X21); giving discounts to avoid critical volume orders (X22); it is envisaged to implement a policy of differentiated discounts, such as not applying a discount policy regardless of the size of the order (X23; X24).

When working with relatively long-term receivables, for categories of debtors: creating conditions for extending the repayment period of debts without interest (X31); to extend the period of receivables through extensions, but in the case of observing strict discipline on the average fixed period (X32); it was not allowed to extend the term of receivables (X33; X34).

Dealing with overdue debtors is also based on a differentiated approach based on their retrospective analysis. In particular, debtors with the highest ratings in previous periods, but with short-term first-time overdue receivables (X41) A decision can be made on a one-time delay without penalty. Or for other types of debtors: delaying payments through fine sanctions (X42; X43); canceling the delivery of goods until payment of accumulated debts (x44) management of overdue receivables is recommended.

Conclusion

As a general conclusion, it can be said that the management of current assets based on the above methods creates the necessary conditions for reducing the volume of finished products in the current assets of the enterprises we are analyzing and increasing the volume of income from sales. As a result, it is possible to increase the turnover and profitability of current assets, to increase the index of fund return compared to non-current assets.

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⁷ Calculated by the author based on analyses.

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